

D5.2 SPOON MONITORING TOOLKIT

WP5, T5.2

AUTHORS: GUDRUN HAINDLMAIER (AIT), SABINE
NEUBERGER (AIT), VITALIY SOLOVIY (AIT), SURYA
KNÖBEL (AIT), BEATRIX WEPNER (AIT)

DISCLAIMER

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under Grant Agreement No. 101182299.

This document has been prepared by SPOON project partners as an account of work carried out within the framework of the EC-GA contract No. 101182299.

Neither the Project Coordinator, nor any signatory party of the SPOON Project Consortium Agreement, nor any person acting on behalf of any of them:

(a) Makes any warranty or representation whatsoever, express or implied:

(i) With respect to the use of any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document, including merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

(ii) That such use does not infringe on or interfere with privately owned rights, including any party's intellectual property.

(iii) That this document is suitable for any particular user's circumstance.

(b) Assumes responsibility for any damages or other liability whatsoever, including any consequential damages, even if the Project Coordinator or any representative of a signatory party of the SPOON Project Consortium Agreement has been advised of the possibility of such damages, resulting from your selection or use of this document or any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document.

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

Project Acronym	SPOON
Project Title	Food Systems in transition – ParticipatOry, Open citizen research for sustainable Nutrition
Project Coordinator	Arlind Xhelili Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP) arlind.xhelili@cscp.org
Project Duration	December 2024 – November 2028 (48 months)

Deliverable No.	D5.2
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 5 - Impact evaluation and monitoring
Task	T5.2
Lead beneficiary	Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	CSCP, SFC, JIBE, EV ILVO, HoC
Due date of deliverable	28.02.2026
Actual submission date	01.03.2026

- *PU = Public
- SEN= sensitive

D5.2 SPOON MONITORING TOOLKIT

CHANGE HISTORY / REVIEW TABLE

v/d	Date	Beneficiary and description	Author
D3	27/02/2026	AIT has submitted the revised toolkit to CSCP and SFC	Guðrun Haindlmaier (AIT), Sabine Neuberger (AIT), Vitaliy Soloviy (AIT), Surya Knöbel (AIT), Beatrix Wepner (AIT)
D2	25/02/2026	AIT, CSCP and SFC discussed the updated toolkit version	Guðrun Haindlmaier (AIT), Vitaliy Soloviy (AIT), Surya Knöbel (AIT), Francesca Grossi (CSCP), Ahmad ur Rehman Hafiz (CSCP), Òscar Larraga (S4C)
D1	13/02/2026	CSCP and SFC provided feedback	Francesca Grossi (CSCP), Ahmad ur Rehman Hafiz (CSCP), Òscar Larraga (S4C)
D1	05/02/2026	The first version of the toolkit is provided to reviewers for feedback	Guðrun Haindlmaier (AIT), Sabine Neuberger (AIT), Vitaliy Soloviy (AIT), Surya Knöbel (AIT), Beatrix Wepner (AIT)
V1	27/02/2026	AIT integrated feedback from reviewers and submitted the deliverable to PC	Guðrun Haindlmaier (AIT), Sabine Neuberger (AIT), Vitaliy Soloviy (AIT), Surya Knöbel (AIT), Beatrix Wepner (AIT)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACRONYMS	7
KEY TERMS	8
1 INTRODUCTION: WHAT IS THIS TOOLKIT ABOUT?	9
2 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES	12
3 DATA COLLECTION OVERVIEW	13
4 EVALUATION QUESTIONS AND INDICATORS	18
5 METHODS AND TOOLS	19
5.1 GETTING TO KNOW THE METHODS	19
5.2 GENERAL MONITORING TOOLS	22
5.2.1 Visual Analogue Scale	20
5.2.2 Participant counting	25
5.2.3 Activity Log	26
5.2.4 Observation checklist for facilitators	27
5.2.5 Reflective prompt cards (end-of-session)	28
5.2.6 Emotional Mapping.....	30
5.2.7 Usage analytics of SPOON Tools	32
5.3 BEHAVIOUR AND PRACTICE-FOCUSED TOOLS	34
5.3.1 Experience sampling method (ESM).....	34
5.3.2 Photovoice	38
5.3.3 Household food waste “mini-audit”	39
5.3.4 Most Significant Change (MSC) stories	41
5.4 TOOLS FOR CO-EVALUATION	42
5.4.1 Assessment rubrics	42
5.4.2 Stakeholder Mapping.....	43
5.4.3. Social network mapping.....	44
5.4.3 Outcome Harvesting (lightweight version).....	46
5.4.4 Ripple Effect Mapping.....	47
6 CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS	48
5 ANNEXES	49
6.1 INDICATOR CATEGORIES	49
6.2 BASELINE EVALUATION TEMPLATE	50

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: SPOON Pathways (schematic representation).....	9
Figure 2: Evaluation framework in practice	11
Figure 3 Monitoring and data collection for evaluation: timeline	14
Figure 4: Three dataflows within SPOON for monitoring and evaluation.....	17

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Provisional list of monitoring methods	11
Table 2 Data collection round, milestones and scope.....	13
Table 3 Main data categories	14
Table 4 SPOON indicators categories (outward).....	18
Table 5 SPOON Monitoring methods and tools.....	20

ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
BCI	Behaviour Change Intervention
CS	Citizen Science
CSL	Citizen Science Lab
DMP	Data Management Plan
ESM	Experience Sampling Method
EU	European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IT	Information Technology
KIP	Key Impact Pathway
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PO	Project Objective
PR	Project Result
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SEF	SPOON Evaluation Framework
WP	Work Package

KEY TERMS

The presented terms are plain language definitions to help readers navigate the document. The interpretation has been tailored and adapted to the SPOON project needs and activities and is aimed primarily as a common reference, without exhaustively capturing the meaning behind the terms. More expansive definitions and descriptions are provided further as necessary.

Term	Basic definition
Sustainable Food System Transformation	A systemic shift toward sustainable, inclusive, and resilient food systems that support healthy diets, reduce environmental harm, and empower communities.
SPOON Evaluation	A collaborative process of evaluating SPOON activities, results, and outcomes that helps to learn along the way, enhance impact potential, and comprehensively evaluate project achievements.
Theory of Change	A conceptual model used in SPOON to articulate how and why change is expected to occur along the impact pathways.
Impact Pathway	A causal set of events describing how activities and outputs lead to outcomes and impacts, in line with project objectives.
Citizen Science Lab (CSL)	A core participatory mechanism of SPOON, which blends citizens science and living lab methods, where citizens act as both researchers and food system change agents.
Behaviour Change Intervention (BCI)	Co-designed and context-specific set of actions in the CSLs regions that aim to experiment, learn, and shift individual or collective food consumption behaviours.
SPOON Digital Toolset	A GDPR-compliant suite of tools, including a questionnaire app, personal data wallet, GDPR-compliant data-sharing platform, and APIs, that enables people to collect, manage, and share their food-related data securely and transparently.
Food environment framework	A model used in SPOON to analyse the contexts in which people interact with food that helps with the identification of intervention points across the food system.

1 INTRODUCTION: WHAT IS THIS TOOLKIT ABOUT?

This toolkit operationalises the SPOON evaluation framework for practical implementation and should be read and used only once project partners have familiarised themselves with the [full framework](#), which provides an outlook on the overall evaluation approach, including theoretical foundation, principles, components, pathways and processes. The framework provides a shared understanding of the project’s impact potential and how partners contribute to it, laying the foundation for monitoring, data collection, and evaluation. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a simplified schematic representation of the assumptions about linkages between activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts, as well as how they link to project objectives.

Figure 1: SPOON Pathways (schematic representation)

SPOON's approach to impact is built around four pathways, detailed in deliverable 5.1. Below, we present their summary for orientation

Pathway 1: Understanding Food System Transformations

This pathway focuses on generating relevant and context-specific knowledge of local food environments through background research, citizen science and co-creation. It gathers and analyses data on food consumption, access, and behaviours to uncover barriers and drivers of

healthy and sustainable eating. By linking citizens, researchers, and policymakers, it builds an evidence base that supports targeted interventions and open knowledge sharing.

Pathway 2: Shaping Food Behaviours

This pathway empowers citizens and communities to make and sustain healthier, more sustainable food choices by engaging with food behaviours, local conditions and social norms. The pathway is implemented through co-designed behavioural change interventions (BCIs) and capacity-building programmes like the SPOON Academy. These efforts strengthen agency, create supportive food environments, and generate policy insights to enhance long-term transformation.

Pathway 3: Promoting Digital Innovation and Data Sharing

SPOON promotes trust, transparency, and inclusion in how food-related data is collected, governed, and shared. It deploys GDPR-compliant digital tools, such as the DataU platform and personal data wallet, to enable citizens to control and use their own data for healthier and more sustainable choices. Together with value chain actors (e.g., retailers, HoReCa, food suppliers), this SPOON toolset enables citizens to generate, control, and share their food data in transparent and empowering ways.

Pathway 4: Empowering Citizens and Decision Makers

This pathway strengthens cross-sector collaboration and citizen participation in food system governance. It supports mutual learning and data-driven decision-making through Citizen Science Living Labs (CSLs), policy recommendations, and capacity-building initiatives. By embedding co-created solutions in real contexts, it enhances citizens' influence on policy, ensures knowledge uptake, and sustains transformation beyond the project timeline.

Building on the framework and the four pathways presented above, this toolkit further details how the evaluation looks in practice. It outlines the relevant procedures, responsibilities, methods and tools for data collection, monitoring and measuring impact (see figure 2). It also describes which evaluation questions and indicators these methods address. Some methods and tools serve to collect data for specific indicators, and others can be flexibly applied across several indicators or to collect complementary evidence.

The methods and indicators outlined here serve to help foster discovery and learning, including a better understanding of project impact potential, identification of unforeseen impacts, making sense and collaborative reflection on project pathways and other processes that help enhance project success, enhance tailoring to local contexts or build shared context for designing BCIs.

Figure 2: Evaluation framework in practice

Table 1 Provisional list of monitoring methods

Type	Description	Methods and tools
General monitoring tools	Polls and tools for real-time feedback and observations; retrospective assessment of behavioural patterns and tangible outcomes; considering participant demographics and expertise levels.	Activity log, participant counts and demographics, pre/post micro survey, prompt cards, observation checklist, usage analytics, reference tracking, emotional mapping
Behaviour & practice change tools	Capture participants' lived experiences, project interactions and behavioural change over time.	Food practice diary, Photo diary / Photovoice, Household food waste “mini-audit”, Experience sampling
Co-creation & empowerment tools	Provide a critical reference for understanding specific contexts of the labs and maps, general stakeholders’ groups, empowerment and indirect impact across labs. Monitors what changes, who benefits and why, adapted to CSL-specific contexts	Outcome Harvesting, Most Significant Change stories, Ripple Effect Mapping, Stakeholder Mapping, Social Network Mapping, Trust & Agency mini-scale, FAIR “readiness” self-assessment

The toolkit has benefited from a co-creative 3-hour workshop that took place on the 27th of February 2025. Throughout the toolkit implementation, feedback loops from CSLs will be built into the process to enable timely adaptations, promote shared ownership, and maintain alignment with SPOON’s overarching goals.

The published toolkit version is considered a shared reference for how monitoring should be implemented until any revised versions are published. The toolkit remains a living document and can be updated through the project in response to emerging insights, changing evaluation needs, as well as new challenges and opportunities. The necessary changes based on WP5 are collected and synthesised by AIT.

2 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

The way this toolkit will be used will depend on the specific roles of the project partners in the project. Further, we detail the description of responsibilities provided in D5.1, with an operational outlook on specific data collection, monitoring and related activities to be implemented by the project partners.

Pilot coordinators are responsible for collecting and submitting relevant data for baseline evaluation, CSL iterations and implementation and evaluation of BCIs. They use the methods provided in this toolkit to collect data and further report on the relevant indicators after each CSL iteration. They are also responsible for timely and consistent data collection from citizens using questionnaires and templates provided by AIT or CSCP. They submit the collected data to the questionnaire sent out by AIT via the SPOON toolset.

Pilot coordinators are also responsible for basic analysis necessary to provide aggregated data along specific indicators, or in case a specific simple index needs to be calculated. Where there is any data manipulation, this should be transparently reported. Pilot coordinators may also engage citizens in co-design of complementary evaluation questions and indicators, collection of auxiliary data based on specific lab activities or participant perspectives. Pilot coordinators invite citizens to participate in the co-evaluation and co-interpretation of findings at the project level during formative evaluation. AIT will ask CSLs to distribute questionnaires (outside of the workshops via the toolset) and support data collection after each iteration in a timely manner.

Work Package leads collect and submit relevant data originating from iteration workshops or during annual formative evaluation based on the activities that fall into the scope of evaluation. They do not carry out any additional monitoring beyond the streamlined data collection relevant to their scope. However, they might be responsible for providing data already reported to them by the CSLs in order to avoid double reporting by pilot coordinators, such as the data on communication activities, as outlined in the next section.

Jibe provides the support necessary to ensure that the data from the SPOON digital tools is collected in ways that enable further disaggregation and organisation to facilitate analysis. This includes enabling encoding specific questions to SPOON pathways, CSLs or data collection rounds. Auxiliary data clustering and analytical capabilities may be further decided.

AIT is responsible for providing clear sets of questions, indicators, methods and milestones, and necessary capacity building to facilitate smooth and streamlined data collection and monitoring processes. AIT also develops dedicated questionnaires and formats for aggregating data, such as upon CSL iterations or during formative evaluation. AIT analyses the data and shares feedback with project partners during the three formative evaluation rounds (data collection, workshops), as well as during interim evaluation formats as necessary.

AIT also revises the toolkit in line with the timeline provided in the agreement, ensuring that consistency is maintained about core data collection and monitoring activities, while avoiding novelty and adaptation based on new insights, the scope of ongoing activities or other contextual conditions.

3 DATA COLLECTION OVERVIEW

Data is collected continuously by project partners based on their activities, results and early observed outcomes. The data is collected across seven rounds, aligned with the overall project timeline to ensure that the analysis of data can inform adjustment of the follow-up activities, as outlined in Table 2 and Figure 3. The data collection rounds usually take place following a specific CSL iteration, while the second, fourth and sixth data collection rounds are also aligned with formative evaluation formats to ensure streamlined processes.

Table 2 Data collection round, milestones and scope (timing to be adjusted, not definitied)

Round	When	What	Description
1	M16 Q1 2026	Baseline & CSL-1	Baseline evaluation: starting conditions across the CSLs and their pilot regions are assessed. This coincides in time with data collection based on the first CSL iteration.
2	M19 Q2 2026	CSL-2 & FE-1	The first Formative evaluation connects learnings from the first two CSL iterations. It also includes a reflection on baseline conditions and how they changed since the project's start, and how insights can enhance CSL's impact potential.
3	M25 Q4 2026	CSL-3	Monitoring data from the third CSL iteration, which focuses on food storage, with some tailored evaluation questions
4	M31 Q2 2027	CSL-4 & FE-2	Data from the third and fourth CSL iterations and project-level findings are collected and further reflected upon during the second formative evaluation.
5	M34 Q3 2027	CSL-5 & CO-DESIGN	Collection of data on knowledge transfer, CSL iteration five, and interim reflection on BCI design
6	M43 Q2 2028	BCI-POST & FE-3	Post-BCI data collection; evaluating co-designed interventions paired with third formative evaluation
7	M48 Q3-Q4 2028	Final evaluation	Final evaluation: complete evaluation along the SPOON pathways, including dedicated workshops

The monitoring and data collection timeline is also summarised in Figure 3 (below) which might be adjusted to meet the project needs.

Figure 3 Monitoring and data collection for evaluation: timeline

The evaluation will benefit from a range of data types, in line with the SPOON Data Management Plan. The exact data sources will be further detailed within the Monitoring Toolkit and Formative evaluation activities relevant to the scope of each task and specific evaluation needs, as well as considering data availability and limitations. In SPOON, certain data categories are collected (see Table 3), and the data mainly come from the following broad sources:

- The activities of Work Packages with data collected by WP or task leads (such as regarding the SPOON Academy, outreach and engagement indicators, multi-stakeholder recommendations, etc.).
- The CSLs (Citizen Science Labs): data collected from participants in different regions.
- The SPOON Questionnaire Tool (via the digital toolset): Data are collected through users’ responses to the questionnaire and stored in the questionnaire database. DataU ensures that this is done in a GDPR-compliant way, while the Datalake only stores anonymised questionnaire data.

Table 3 Main data categories

Data categories	Description
Consumer behaviour data	Information on how people plan, buy, store, prepare, eat, and dispose of food.
Demographic data	Basic participant characteristics such as age, gender, education, household type, and socio-economic profile.
Consent and engagement data	Records of participant agreements on data sharing, frequency of contributions, and interaction with the toolset.

Personal/sensitive data	Limited information that may qualify as personal data under GDPR (e.g., behavioural or demographic data that can make individuals identifiable). No highly sensitive categories (e.g., health, religion) are planned at this stage.
Structured workshop outputs	Data collected systematically through CSL workshops, questionnaires, or defined protocols (e.g., responses to food journey stages).
Unstructured participant contributions	Spontaneous observations, reflections, and qualitative insights shared during CSL activities or through the Digital Toolset.
Digital interaction data	Usage logs and feedback from the SPOON Digital Toolset (questionnaire tool, DataU, Wallet, Dashboard, DataLake).
Qualitative feedback	Participant reflections and outputs from SPOON Academy trainings, peer learning, and knowledge transfer activities.

Data collection is organised on two levels, aligned with the project work plan and the CSL iteration cycles. At the **CSL level**, the data collection runs from baseline evaluation through and follows the CSL iterations and the associated Behaviour Change Interventions (BCIs). Within each iteration, data are gathered from the pilot coordinators or other partners who systematise data submitted by CSL (e.g. on CLS activities, communications, tool usage).

At the **project level**, data collection takes place along the timeline of formative evaluations, including at least two formative evaluation iterations and one final iteration. This data involves an outlook on overall project activities (implementation progress, learning, synthesis across CSLs) and long-term, outcome-based impact evaluation.

Data collection set-up for monitoring and evaluation:

Building on the roles defined in Chapter 2, data collection for monitoring and evaluation is implemented through coordinated workshop documentation, questionnaire-based citizen data collection, and project-level reporting by WPs. Data are consolidated for formative evaluation and synthesis across CSLs and work packages.

- **CSL implementation evidence:** pilot coordinators document session implementation (e.g., timing, participation, engagement) and capture workshop outputs generated by participants using the toolkit methods and standardised templates.
- **CSL and citizen-generated data:** participants provide structured inputs by completing questionnaires via the SPOON Questionnaire Tool, supported by pilot coordinators for distribution and contextual roll-out.
- **Standardised reporting:** CSCP provides guidance and templates; pilot coordinators compile workshop outputs and implementation evidence using these templates to ensure comparability across sites.
- **Project-level reporting and outreach indicators:** WP leads submit WP-specific indicators to AIT based on their activities/outputs;

- **Handover and synthesis:** pilot coordinators submit compiled workshop reports to CSCP for synthesis and translation into English. CSCP then submits these results to AIT for analysis of the inputs.
- **Formative evaluation feedback loops:** after each CSL iteration, AIT and pilot coordinators exchange for reflection on progress and challenges, enabling conditions, capacity gaps, and course corrections aimed at impact enhancement.
- **Data storage and overview:** Evaluation findings are stored in the WP5 project folder.

Three dataflows and data management pipelines (See figure 4):

Data collection and reporting flow across SPOON monitoring and evaluation. The figure shows three parallel dataflows and how responsibilities are distributed across project roles from design and distribution through collection & submission to synthesis. **Dataflow 1** covers workshop/iteration templates co-designed by AIT and WP leads and completed by pilot coordinators; **Dataflow 2** covers project level evaluation with AIT-led questionnaires with split submissions from pilot coordinators and WP leads; and **Dataflow 3** covers citizen-facing questionnaires distributed via CSLs, with responses stored and structured in the SPOON questionnaire database before being accessed by AIT for analysis and synthesis.

1. **CSL workshop activity templates and implementation:** CSCP (in coordination with AIT, where needed) designs or co-designs standardised workshop templates and instructions aligned with the SPOON monitoring toolkit indicators and iteration topics. WP leads (e.g., CSCP or SFC) distribute these materials to pilot coordinators. The pilot coordinators then collect and submit:
 - (i) Workshop implementation data (e.g., timing, number of participants or demographic data, engagement)
 - (ii) Workshop outputs generated by participants (e.g., discussion outputs, reflections, co-creation results).

Where relevant, CSCP supports harmonisation and SFC quality checks of workshop reporting to ensure cross-CSL consistency before synthesis (translation to English included). AIT receives these inputs at the end of the process and uses them for synthesis and analysis, providing feedback during formative evaluation and interim formats as needed.

2. **Project-level evaluation:** In dataflow 2, AIT coordinates and organises project-level data collection in line with the evaluation questions and indicators. AIT defines the required information, designs the respective data collection instruments (e.g., questionnaires configured in the SPOON Questionnaire Tool and/or targeted data requests via other means), and assigns responsibilities based on where the information is operationally available. Work Package (WP) leads provide inputs that originate from their WP activities and outputs (such as capacity-building activities and communication/outreach metrics). In parallel, pilot coordinators provide project-level information that sits at the CSL level but goes beyond individual behavioural citizen data, e.g., evidence on CSL implementation, governance and coordination arrangements, stakeholder/policy outreach, enabling conditions, and local outcomes relevant to the project-level impact pathways. AIT collects these contributions through

the agreed formats and timelines and consolidates them into a project-wide synthesis for evaluation and reporting.

3. **Citizen-generated structured data:** AIT develops questionnaires and configures them in the SPOON Questionnaire Tool. Pilot coordinators distribute the questionnaire link to citizens and support contextual tailoring and practical implementation in the pilot regions. Citizens generate structured data by responding in the Questionnaire Tool. The resulting data are routed from the Questionnaire Tool to the questionnaire database, which is managed by Jibe. There, the responses are anonymised and tagged with basic metadata, such as pilot site, CSL iteration/timepoint and questionnaire version, to support analysis. AIT then downloads the structured datasets (e.g. CSV exports) from the database for evaluation and analysis.

Figure 4: Three dataflows within SPOON for monitoring and evaluation

4 EVALUATION QUESTIONS AND INDICATORS

Each SPOON pathway has a specific scope, linked to a set of objectives, activities, results, expected outcomes and indicators. This allows WPs and pilot coordinators to make clear connections between pathways and their activities. Evaluation questions are structured along the SPOON pathways. Each question is operationalised through core and complementary indicators. Collection of data on indicators is supported through plain language questions.

Data on those questions is continuously collected via concurrent channels outlined earlier and submitted to AIT during specific instances. Each indicator comes with an underlying ontology, which includes categories that partners will see as provided in Table 3, and categories used for monitoring and data management purposes provided in Annex 6.1. The first set of evaluation questions and indicators is expected to be ready in Q1 2026, while complementary questions can be identified for specific CSLs at later stages.

As part of setting up the data collection processes, following the toolkit publication, partners would be informed on the general data collection timeline, meaning who is expected to report when and on what indicators, creating predictability and enabling streamlined data collection. Once the data collection procedures are set up, adjustments may still be made to address new developments or unforeseen conditions.

Project partners will mostly need to trace only a narrow range of indicators relevant to the scope of their activities. Most evaluation questions feature both qualitative and quantitative indicators, enabling partners and stakeholders to participate in the sense-making and reflection around observed processes, changes and issues.

Table 4 SPOON indicators categories (outward)

Category	What does this mean?
Name	A short name for shared orientation
Guiding question	Indicators will be communicated to partners in plain language questions to facilitate the data collection process.
Guidance	Including types of data needed, scales and units of analysis.
Method	Lists one of the methods used to collect relevant indicator data.
Responsible	Project partner responsible for data collection and submission.
Level	Project-level data collected, CSL data, and individual citizen data.

5 METHODS AND TOOLS

The methods and tools presented in this chapter can be used to collect data to address relevant evaluation questions during CSL iterations and in preparation for the formative evaluation. These methods are designed to be engaging and user-friendly, supporting both high-frequency monitoring and deeper reflection. An initial core set of methods and tools outlined in this toolkit is complemented with those identified or used by CSLs to address their specific questions, activities and indicators, reflecting the interplay of top-down, bottom-up and exploratory evaluation. The data collected via these methods and tools will be aggregated and synthesised through questionnaires, interviews, and workshops.

5.1 GETTING TO KNOW THE METHODS

Every method of the Monitoring Toolkit is presented following the same structured form:

Ready-made /needs customisation	Tool name	
Licence needed/open source		
Digital/analogue		
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualisation, interaction setup)		
Target group (s):	Data type collected	
Time of use (project phase – exploration, testing, implementation, monitoring, at the end of the activity)		
Timing (one-time data collection, before-and-after, continuous)	individual change or aggregated data	
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions
acknowledging complexity	power sensitiveness	outcome-focused evaluation
Effort (time, persons, material)		
Detailed description		What?
		Why?
		How?
Templates (links to material or pictures)		
Relevant indicators (list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference) ¹		
Examples (external links)		

The tools and methods listed below will be updated or changed according to the needs of the CSLs and the project partners as the project develops. In case some methods and tools turn out unnecessary, they might also be moved to an annex as complementary methods or for later use and scaling purposes outside the SPOON project.

The Toolkit comprises different types of tools, namely (1) general easy-to-run/light touch tools; (2) Behaviour & practice change tools; as well as (3) Co-Creation and Empowerment tools. Within each of the three types of tools, there are some core (mandatory) tools as well as optional (recommended, based on the respective CSL context) ones.

¹ The relevant indicators will be added in the next revision of the Monitoring Toolkit into each form describing the individual tools and methods

Citizens can use the information they record about themselves in the SPOON Food Journal as input during the workshops and or in responding to questions. The Food Journal is, however, not a monitoring tool per se.

Table 5 SPOON Monitoring methods and tools

General easy-to-run tools				
Use	Tool	Captures	Monitoring output	Users
C	Activity Log	Documents activity details for each intervention	Supports formative monitoring, comparability across CSLs, and learning	ALL
O	Participant Counting	Number and demographics of participants in specific activities	Quick quantitative counts of participation (WP4 template on demographics)	ALL
C	Micro-survey (5–10 items)	Changes in understanding food systems, self-reported behaviour change, trust, acceptance, perception	Quantitative data for an easy-to-analyse status quo	PC
C	Observation checklist for facilitators	Feasibility, inclusiveness, quality of participation, engagement dynamics, barriers and enablers	Summary of observations per CSL iteration, including recurring patterns and unconventional examples	ALL
C	Usage analytics	Usage analytics for tools from WP 2 (who, what, when, etc.)	AIT uses the outputs for evaluation, and CSLs may view dashboards	WP 2
O	Reflective prompt cards (end-of-session)	Unexpected insights, perceived relevance to local conditions, learning outcomes, and intentions	Qualitative “pulse” data that is quick to analyse and comparable across CSLs.	PC
O	Emotional Mapping	Emotional attachment to food practices, reactions to new practices	Mapping of emotional associations to specific issues or aspects of food environments	PC
Behaviour & practice change tools (food journey, food waste, sustainable choices)				
Use	Tool	Captures	Monitoring Output	Users
C	Experience sampling method	Captures dynamic changes in motivation, engagement, and learning during participation, barriers and enablers for participation	Collect contextual and situational data, as well as usage data on SPOON tools.	ALL
O	Photo diary / Photovoice	Context-specific challenges, cultural meanings, barriers, drivers, unexpected patterns.	Generates new research topics and evidence for dissemination	PC
O	Household food waste “mini-audit”	Self-reported counts, simple kitchen caddy weigh-days, bin snapshots	Maps to reduction in waste, adoption of waste-reduction practices.	PC

Co-creation + empowerment tools (what changes, who benefits, why)				
Use	Tool	Captures	Monitoring Output	Users
C	Stakeholder analysis	provides a critical reference for understanding specific contexts of the labs and maps general stakeholder groups across labs.	serves as important element of baseline evaluation and for continuous monitoring and reflection	PC
C	Assessment rubrics	Short rubric partners complete, such as FAIR readiness assessment when producing datasets/outputs (metadata, licensing, accessibility).	Could be used to measures the FAIR compliance indicator, and for other purposes	ALL
C	Outcome Harvesting (lightweight version)	Project partners document “outcomes”, e.g. changes in behaviour, relationships, policy interest) and the project contribution	Reflection at end of project/activity; assessment of change potentials	WP
O	Most Significant Change (MSC) stories	empowerment, social learning, ripple effects to family/community, broader societal effects	short stories of the most important change citizens or participants experienced	ALL
O	Ripple Effect Mapping	facilitated mapping session that surfaces indirect impacts: networks formed, advocacy, new initiatives	Directly supports indicators on networks, follow-on initiatives, civic action	ALL
O	Social Network Mapping	Pre/post mapping of collaborations (citizens–researchers–policy–business–CSOs)	visualises “new collaborations” and “two-way communication” indicators	ALL

(PC – pilot coordinator, WP – WP and task leads, ALL – all project partners in relevant instances; C – Core, O – optional)

Within WP5, selected analytical methods will be applied to the SPOON monitoring work to make sense of the data gathered through the Monitoring Toolkit and the additional monitoring inputs provided by Pilot coordinators and WP leads. These analyses are led by AIT and will help consolidate and interpret evidence across pilots, identify patterns and trends, and close remaining data gaps where needed using complementary evidence obtained via desk research, document analysis, semi-structured interviews, and using thematic analysis, statistical calculations and triangulation across different sources of evidence.

Semi-structured interviews may be used also by Pilot coordinators or project partners to deepen understanding of specific issues or needs, and individual experiences. AIT will use them for baseline and formative evaluation. Thematic analysis will help to analyse workshop reports to systematise findings and elicit recurring themes, issues, enablers, challenges or good practices. Exchanges between WP5 and SPOON work packages and project partners will contribute to capacity building and help enhance monitoring and data collection activities.

5.2 GENERAL MONITORING TOOLS

5.2.1 Visual Analog Scale

Ready-made/needs to be customized	Visual Analog Scale (for pre/post surveys)	
Licence needed/open source		
Digital & analog		
Possible adaptation levels: easy to be translated into any language; format and interaction setup should be kept as outlined below		
Target group (s): Participants in an intervention/activity (e.g., workshop, training, community event, citizen science activity) - Can be used with adults, youth, and mixed groups; also suitable for facilitators/implementers as self-assessment - Optional: specific stakeholder groups (consumers, food service staff, farmers, students)		Data type collected Metric data
Time of use: - Implementation monitoring: quick pulse-check during a series of sessions - End of activity/event: immediate learning outcome assessment - Follow-up : to see retention (e.g., 2–8 weeks after)		Captures individual change or aggregated data
Timing: Before-after (pre/post) around the intervention/activity		
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions once available.
acknowledging complexity	/	
Effort (time, persons, material) Time: ~2–5 min per participant per measurement point (pre or post); add ~5–10 min for explanation the first time - People: 1 facilitator to administer; 1 person for data entry/analysis (can be same) - Material: paper VAS (10 cm line) + pen + ruler, OR digital slider (tablet/phone/online survey)		

<p>- Data processing: measure in mm (0–100) or export slider values; basic spreadsheet analysis</p>	
<p>Detailed description</p> <p>A Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) captures a subjective judgement on a continuous line anchored by two extremes. For food-system interventions, it can be used to measure perceived <i>*awareness*</i> or <i>*self-assessed knowledge*</i> about food topics (e.g., seasonality, food waste, labels, sustainable diets) before and after an activity.</p> <hr/> <p>- Very quick and low-burden: good for busy events and repeated measurement.</p> <p>- Sensitive to small changes and avoids coarse categories (useful for short learning interventions).</p> <p>- Produces metric data (0–100) that is easy to compare pre/post and across groups.</p> <p>- Works on paper or digitally; integrates well into participatory/citizen science settings.</p> <hr/> <p>1) Define the construct(s): e.g., awareness of food-system impacts, confidence in reading labels, knowledge of seasonal foods.</p> <p>2) Draft 3–8 short VAS items (one construct per line). Use clear anchors (e.g., “not at all aware” ↔ “very aware”).</p> <p>3) Administer PRE (before activity or workshop). Give a short instruction and a neutral example.</p> <p>4) Administer POST (immediately after activity or workshop). Keep wording identical. If time is tight during a workshop, repeat in another workshop at a later stage.</p> <p>5) Scoring: paper: measure the mark’s distance from the left anchor in mm (0–100); digital: export slider value.</p> <p>6) Analysis: compute pre/post differences per item (mean/median, distribution); optionally disaggregate by subgroup (e.g., age, prior experience) and report equity-relevant patterns.</p> <p>7) Good practice: ensure accessibility (large print, clear language), allow “I don’t know / not applicable” when needed, and avoid leading anchors.</p>	<p>What?</p>
	<p>Why?</p>
	<p>How?</p>
<p>Templates</p> <p>- “How aware are you of how food choices affect climate and biodiversity?” (not at all aware ↔ very aware)</p> <p>- “How confident are you that you can identify seasonal fruits/vegetables in your region?” (not confident ↔ very confident)</p>	

- “How well do you understand food date labels (best before/use by)?” (not at all ↔ very well)
- “How much do you know about ways to reduce household food waste?” (nothing ↔ a lot)

Examples (external links)

Visual analog scale

Graphic rating scale

(Numeric) rating scale

https://methods.sagepub.com/ency/edvol/sage-encyclopedia-of-educational-research-measurement-evaluation/chpt/visual-analog-scales#_

5.2.2 Participant counting

Ready-made template provided by CSCP	Participant counting	
Licence needed/open source: /		
Digital/analogue: analogue but will be digitalized as part of reporting by pilot coordinators to CSCP		
Possible adaptation levels: Adapt counting rules (unique vs. repeat), disaggregation (target groups, gender/age), frequency (per activity / weekly / per iteration), and privacy level (anonymous counts vs. pseudonymised IDs). Language can be kept in English.		
Target group (s): Pilot coordinators, citizens, CSCP synthesis		
Time of use: before or after each workshop.		
Timing: continuous (per workshop)		Captures participation rates
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions
/	/	
Effort: low effort. 2–5 min per activity (1 person). Material: simple spreadsheet/form or template provided by CSCP; optional sign-in list (paper/tablet) or registration export.		
Detailed description Assign a counting owner per CSL/site or workshop. Record participation immediately after each activity using agreed rules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Count unique participants (first-time) and returning participants (repeat attendance). Distinguish registered vs. attended (and, if relevant, drop-outs/no-shows). Review counts at milestones (end of iteration; midterm; final) to assess reach, continuity, and gaps.		What? Who participated, how many, and how often (unique vs. repeat).
		Why? To evidence reach and inclusiveness,
		How? Standardised counting rules + simple form/table per workshop
Templates CSCP templates		
Examples (external links)		

5.2.3 Activity Log

Needs to be customized	Activity log		
Open source: Excel/Sheets/Form			
Digital/analogue			
Possible adaptation levels: Adapt fields (activity types, CSL iteration etc.), level of detail, and frequency; language can be kept in English			
Target group (s): CSL facilitators; project partners implementing activities; WP/task leads	Data type collected Short qualitative notes + structured categorical fields		
Time of use: completed after each activity/session; at any point in the project			
Timing: Continuous (after each activity) + periodic review (e.g., monthly/after each CSL iteration)	Aggregated data		
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions	
/	/		
Effort: 5–10 min per activity (1 person). Material: simple spreadsheet/form; optional attachments (agenda, photos, outputs)			
Detailed description Assign a log owner per CSL or project task. Fill in immediately after each activity using agreed categories (activity type, pathway, target group). Review at milestones (end of iteration; midterm; final).			What?
			Why?
			How?
Templates Simple table fields: ID; date; CSL/site; activity type; pathway tag(s); objective; target group; #participants; facilitation notes; key outputs; adaptations; risks/issues; follow-upD actions.			
Examples (external links)			

5.2.4 Observation checklist for facilitators

Needs to be customized for each iteration topic	Observation check-list	
Open source		
Digital/analogue: Flexible		
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualization, interaction setup) Possible to focus on specific group dynamics or tool usability		
Target group (s): Pilot coordinators		Data type collected
Time of use (During and immediately after a CSL session)		Qualitative notes and ordinal scales
Timing (Continuous (collected during every workshop))		Captures group dynamics and aggregated behavioral patterns
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions
acknowledging complexity	power sensitiveness	/
Effort (time, persons, material) requires a separate person who observes and makes notes, also time for preparation and analysis		
<p>Detailed description</p> <p>1. Prepare your checklist On a sheet of paper list 5 to 10 simple yes/no or spot-on/needs-work items tied to your workshop goals—for example, "Everyone participates?" or "Does the group stay on topic?". Keep space for quick notes.</p> <p>2. Observe and check during the workshop During the workshop, Tick off items on your checklist without interrupting, note from observation. You can have two observers taking turns to make it less dependent on subjective judgements.</p> <p>3. Review and share insights Share 2 to 3 key takeaways with the group. Use it to tweak the rest of the workshop or future iterations</p>		<p>What? A structured observation form used by facilitators or designated observers to record real-time dynamics, participant engagement, and technical hurdles that might not be captured in self-reported surveys.</p> <p>Why? Helps to observe how the group reacts to specific digital tools or workshop formats, identify power imbalances and trace group dynamics.</p> <p>How? A second facilitator or observer uses the checklist to mark specific behaviors. They look for signals like "high enthusiasm during the mapping task" or "frustration when using the data wallet." They also note "critical incidents"—moments of significant disagreement or sudden breakthroughs in understanding</p>
Templates (links to material or pictures)		

Relevant indicators (list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference)
Examples (external links)

5.2.5 Reflective prompt cards (end-of-session)

Ready-made	Tool name Reflective Prompt Cards	
Open source		
Digital/analogue: can be both		
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualization, interaction setup) Can be adapted to any language and level of visualization/skill level (easy to engage also less verbal groups)		
Target group (s): citizens, any CSL participants , workshop participants		Data type collected Qualitative assessments, rankings
Time of use (project phase – exploration, testing, implementation monitoring, at end of activity) all		
Timing (one-time data collection, before-after, continuous) One time data collection after an activity		Captures individual opinions
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions
/	power sensitiveness	outcome-focused evaluation
Effort (time, persons, material) 15-45mins; 1 facilitator (depending on group size), prepared cards, option for display of cards (wall etc.)		
Detailed description: Collecting written feedback can become visual when turning cards into patterns through colors, placement or clustering. Also, when using a visual based canvas for placing cards. Giving participants the possibility to turn written feedback into voting or ranking at the same time and allowing for anonymous opinions. What can be measured? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rather than measuring, feedback allows for sharing of opinions, sentiments, satisfaction or disagreement - It allows prioritisation and ranking of importance or preferences - Collection of wishes, needs, etc. 		What? Why?
How to apply the method? 1) Prepare the cards		How?

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decide what you want feedback on (e.g., learning, relevance to daily food practices, feasibility of solutions, inclusiveness, trust in tools/data use). • Choose 3–6 prompts (keep wording simple). Print on cards or prepare a digital equivalent (e.g., Miro/Mural/Padlet/Google Form). • If you want ranking, prepare a canvas (paper poster or digital board) with columns such as: “<i>Worked well</i>” / “<i>Needs improvement</i>” / “<i>Next steps</i>” or a scale (e.g., <i>Low</i> → <i>High</i>). <p>2) Introduce the activity (2 min)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain that the goal is to capture honest reflections and priorities, not “right answers.” <p>3) Individual reflection (5–8 min)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give each participant 2–3 cards (or digital prompts). • Ask them to respond to reflection questions such as (by picking a prompt card): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ “One thing I learned about food systems today is...” ○ “One thing I will try / do differently is...” ○ “A barrier in my daily life is...” ○ “One thing that would make this easier for people like me is...” ○ “I felt included / heard when...” <p>4) Make it visual (5–10 min)</p> <p>Choose one of these quick formats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clustering wall: Participants place cards on a wall/board and group similar ones together (by theme). • Matrix placement: Place cards on a 2×2 or scale canvas (e.g., <i>Impact vs. Feasibility</i>; <i>Easy vs. Hard</i>). • Dot voting / ranking: Everyone gets 3–5 stickers/dots to vote on the most important cards or themes. <p>5) Short sense-making (5–10 min)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask participants to comment on emerging clusters: “What do you notice?” “Which theme matters most?” • If time is short, facilitators can do clustering afterwards and just capture the raw cards. • Optional: use additional (colored) feedback cards to collect additional prompts: Encourage short, concrete statements (1–2 sentences) and optional symbols/drawings for less verbal groups <p>6) Document the output</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take clear photos/screenshots • Record basic metadata: date, CSL, activity type, number of participants, target group, language, and whether anonymous. • Store cards securely (especially if any personal data is included). 	
<p>Templates (links to material or pictures)</p>	

Relevant indicators (list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference)

Examples (external links)

5.2.6 Emotional Mapping

Needs to be customized	Emotional Mapping
Open source	
Digital & analog	
Possible adaptation levels: easy to be translated into any language; format and interaction setup should be kept as outlined below	
Target group (s): - Citizens/consumers in the target area (incl. youth, elderly, vulnerable groups) - Participants of behavioural change interventions (e.g., canteen users, community garden members). - Citizen scientists and community representatives; optionally local food actors and municipal staff for a multi-perspective map	Data type collected Georeferenced qualitative data: mapped points/areas linked to emotion categories (colour-coded) plus short explanations/comments (optional: photos, participant metadata)
Time of use: exploration	
Timing: One time (potentially also before-after an intervention)	Captures individual data
Evaluation principle	Link to CSL interventions

acknowledging complexity	/	outcome-focused evaluation	
Effort (time, persons, material)			
Printed or digital maps, pins			
app. 30-45mins (explanation and conduction of mapping)			
Detailed description			What?
<p>Emotional mapping links people’s relationship with specific places in their neighbourhood. The purpose and spatial scope is defined and a base map prepared. A legend describes emotions to be linked with places on the map and participants place pins in the respective colour on the map The exercise follows these steps:</p>			Why?
<p>1) Prepare a base map (printed A3/A4 or digital) and emotional legend 2) Recruit participants and ensure informed consent; clarify that there are no 'right' answers and that sensitive topics may arise. 3) Participants place pins/stickers on locations and label them with emotion categories; add a short explanation for each marker (note cards, short interview, or group discussion). 4) <i>Optional: run separate sessions for different groups (e.g., gender/age, intervention vs. comparison group) or repeat before-after an intervention.</i> 5) Digitise (if analogue) and analyse: identify hotspots, compare groups, code explanations qualitatively, and triangulate with other data (surveys, observations). <i>Optional: Validate findings with participants and discuss actionable implications with implementers/decision makers</i></p>			How?
Templates			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Base map template: printable A3/A4 map (with simple landmarks, scale, north arrow) or a shared digital map - Emotion legend: colour code + short definitions (adapt to context; include 'neutral/uncertain') - Prompt sheet: 3-6 guiding questions tailored to the food system topic (e.g., where do you enjoy buying food, where do you feel excluded, where is food waste visible?) - Consent + privacy note: guidance on not marking private addresses and on handling sensitive stories <p>Digital options: Google My Maps, Maptionnaire, ArcGIS Survey123, Miro/Mural (map background + stickers)</p>			
Examples (external links)			

<http://urbantoolkit.eu/de/werkzeuge-und-methoden/landkarte-der-emotionen/>

5.2.7 Usage analytics of SPOON Tools

Ready-made infrastructure with needed configuration for workshops and tools	Usage analytics	
Licence needed/open source SPOON Tool		
Digital		
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualization, interaction setup) Adapt: which tools are tracked, workshop definitions (login, usage count, submission, feature use), aggregation level (daily/weekly/per iteration), segmentation (pilot site, iteration, user role), privacy settings (anonymisation/pseudonymisation, retention), dashboard views vs. export formats (CSV), and frequency of reporting.		
Target group (s): Time of use (project phase – exploration, testing, implementation monitoring, at end of activity) WP2 technical team (data generation/aggregation); AIT (evaluation use); CSL coordinators (optional viewing of dashboards)		Data type collected System-generated log/workshop data (timestamps, workshop type, tool, counts) + aggregated usage metrics (e.g., active users, completion rates)

Timing (one-time data collection, before-after, continuous) After each iteration and continuous for usage metrics		Captures individual change or aggregated data
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions
/	/	
Effort (time, persons, material) CSL effort: low (using the tools, viewing dashboards is optional) Setup/maintenance: medium (WP2 to defines what to monitor, ensure privacy, maintain database) Analysis: low–medium (AIT reviews trends and triangulates with activity logs and qualitative feedback)		
Detailed description Usage analytics summarise how WP2 tools are used over time and by whom (e.g., who uses what, when, and how often). Outputs can be shared as aggregated dashboards and/or export files that AIT uses to interpret tool adoption, engagement patterns, and potential bottlenecks.	What? Aggregated indicators of tool usage (active users, frequency, feature use, drop-out)	
	Why? Evaluate uptake and engagement with digital tools and detect barriers of implementation.	
	How? WP2 configures usage tracking and privacy settings, potentially generates dashboards or exports	
Templates (links to material or pictures) Suggested export fields (example): date/time, pilot site, iteration/timepoint, usage (if available), tool/module, workshop type, count Optional: Dashboard screenshots/standard view definitions (to be added)		
Relevant indicators (list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference) ² <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool uptake and sustained use (adoption/retention) • Engagement intensity (“dosage”/exposure to digital components) • Implementation barriers/enablers related to digital tooling (e.g., drop-off patterns) 		
Examples (external links)		

² The relevant indicators will be added in the next revision of the Monitoring Toolkit into each form describing the individual tools and methods

5.3 BEHAVIOUR AND PRACTICE-FOCUSED TOOLS

5.3.1 Experience sampling method (ESM)

Needs to be customized	Experience Sampling Method (ESM)	
Licence needed/open source		
Digital (can be configured within the SPOON questionnaire)		
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualization, interaction setup)		
Target group (s): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen scientists documenting food waste, food access, or sustainable food practices • Community members engaged in citizen science activities • Project coordinators can also be included for reflective monitoring 	Data type collected: Scale data (Likert-type) Categorical data Open text Photo uploads	
Time of use: Implementation monitoring (to capture ongoing experiences during project participation). Could be a quick check up after or before each iteration workshop. If not sent out regularly, it is difficult to measure continuous changes. Evaluation (for longitudinal tracking of motivation, learning, engagement)		
Timing: Continuous, moment-based data collection. As its short, can be applied fast. Random or stratified intervals throughout a day/week	Captures individual change	
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions
/	power sensitiveness	
Effort Setup: development/customization of app & questionnaire (in questionnaire builder to be designed per CSL) (~1–2 months). Here the SPOON questionnaire tool can be used for mini surveys.		

<p>Data collection: minimal per participant (1–3 minutes per prompt, multiple times per week)</p> <p>Analysis: requires expertise in handling longitudinal data (also depending on datatype if images or text etc.)</p> <p>Personnel: 1–2 researchers/assistants for monitoring + analysis</p> <p>Material: smartphones and SPOON tools, data storage (Datalake)</p>	
<p>Detailed description</p> <p>A set of procedures for collecting real-time data about people's feelings, thoughts, and behaviors as they naturally occur in their daily lives. How it monitors: It monitors fluctuations in citizens states (stress, mood, fatigue) or contextual data (location, activity) by capturing the data in the moment, reducing retrospective bias. It's highly effective for monitoring variables that change rapidly or are difficult to recall later.</p> <p>The Experience Sampling Method (Larson & Csikszentmihalyi 2014) is a real-time self-report technique where participants receive random prompts (“beeps”) on their phone and fill out short questionnaires about their current situation, emotions, and activities.</p> <p>Question examples:</p> <p>Example ESM questionnaire:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What did you eat for lunch?</i> <p>How did you decide to buy what you have in your fridge?</p>	<p>What?</p> <p>Collect contextual and situational data</p>
	<p>Why?</p> <p>Captures dynamic changes in motivation, engagement, and learning during participation</p> <p>Helps identify barriers and enablers for sustained citizen science involvement</p> <p>Particularly relevant for food system projects, where participation intersects with everyday practices (shopping, cooking, food disposal)</p>
	<p>How?</p> <p>Usage of SPOON tools. Participants receive the link with one or two questions, which are repeated at several different stages. At each prompt, they complete a 1–2 minute questionnaire (context, activity, mood, perceived learning, motivation).</p>
<p>Templates</p>	

**Actual Intake:
ESM as alternative to food record**

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN:
Questions: short recall - assessment of dietary intake of past 2 hours
Answer options: open field: reporting exact type and quantity of foods consumed

BEEP SCHEDULE:
Fixed
8 AM ————— 10 PM
Fixed sampling approach = sample every time window (e.g. every 2 hrs) = sample every eating episode (cfr. food record)

DURATION:
1# beeps/day = 1sampling period (risk of reporting fatigue): max. 4-7 days

EXAMPLE:
4 days of fixed ESM sampling with beeps every 2 hours to report dietary intake during past 2 hours

**Habitual intake:
ESM as alternative to FFQ or 24hr Recalls**

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN:
Questions: short recall - assessment of dietary intake of past 2 hours
Answer options: multiple choice: reporting type and estimated quantity of food groups consumed (e.g. based on food groups and quantity options of FFQ)

BEEP SCHEDULE:
Semi-random
8 AM ————— 10 PM
Fixed or semi-random sampling approach : e.g. 2-3 beeps per day = sample 2-3 time windows/day, but every time window sampled multiple times during sampling period

DURATION:
1# beeps/day (lower burden) = 1sampling period: up to 1 month

EXAMPLE:
2 weeks of semi-random ESM sampling with 2-3 beeps a day to report dietary intake during past 2 hours. Example sampling scheme where every time window is sampled 5 times during 2 weeks:

https://media.springernature.com/full/springer-static/image/art%3A10.1186%2Fs12966-024-01643-1/MediaObjects/12966_2024_1643_Fig2_HTML.png?as=webp

Examples (external links)

- YAPES – Young Adults’ Political Experience Sampling (Prof. Jörg Matthes (Project lead)) – Objective: It is becoming increasingly difficult for scientists to determine how, where and through which sources young people are exposed to politics. The aim of YAPES is to enable young people themselves to explore this question. Method: Interested young people were invited to collect their political experiences on a daily basis and send them to the research team via email or WhatsApp. Anything they found politically interesting and relevant could be quickly and easily photographed, documented and commented on. This made it possible to determine which political issues young people address in their everyday lives and how they are reached by politics. [YAPES – Young Adults’ Political Experience Sampling](#)
- Barbi Seme from the Luna project: This project explores the lived experiences of menstrual cycles using Experience Sampling Methodology (ESM). They engage with citizen scientists to track their daily experiences via a mobile app to better understand the experiential dynamics throughout the cycle, deepen self-knowledge, and advocate for supportive environments and policies. It aims to comprehensively understand the dynamic changes throughout the menstrual cycle. [IMPETUS- CSI Fact Sheets](#)
- Joint Danube Survey 5: [Citizen Science - Let's Go Sampling Together! | Danube Survey - ICPDR](#) – Students are encouraged to teachers and students to document their experience with photos and videos! Schools that tag us on social media will have a chance to be featured on our official pages.

[Experience Sampling as a dietary assessment method: a scoping review towards implementation | International Journal of Behavioural Nutrition and Physical Activity | Full Text](#)

5.3.2 Photovoice

Needs to be customised	Photovoice	
Licence needed/open source: No licence needed for the method as such. Requires clear consent and photo rights/ethics procedures.		
Digital/analogue: both smartphones/cameras; printed photos for workshops; digital gallery optional		
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualisation, interaction setup): Adapt the photo assignment (theme + guiding questions), language, duration (days/weeks), and output format (workshop discussion, exhibition, story map, policy brief). Adapt safeguarding/consent to local context.		
Target group (s): Citizen scientists/community members (incl. underrepresented groups); optionally invite local stakeholders/policymakers to a reflection/exhibition session	Data type collected Participant-generated photos + captions/short stories (optional: workshop discussion notes)	
Time of use (project phase – exploration, testing, implementation monitoring, at end of activity): Best in exploration/problem framing (to surface lived experience). Can also be used at end of an iteration to document perceived change and lessons learned		
Timing (one-time data collection, before-after, continuous): One cycle typically: photo period (duration between 1–14 days), plus facilitated workshop; can be repeated across iterations	Captures individual perspectives and experiences	
Evaluation principle	Link to CSL interventions: Use to understand local food environments and practices..	
/	power sensitiveness	/
Effort (time, persons, material): Preparation 1–2 h; participant photo period 0.5–1 h; workshop(s) 2–3 h; synthesis 2–6 h (depending on depth). Materials: phones/cameras, printing , consent forms, facilitation space.		
Detailed description Create a Photo assignment sheet (theme + do/don't) Prepare consent + image release form as well as caption template (can be supported by an app) Inform participants about the assignment and modalities (provide a take-away guide with guiding questions); include short basic training on photography Optional for workshop setting on results of collected photos: theme clustering matrix; outputs template (1-page story per theme).	What?	
	Why?	
	How?	

Prepare exhibition (online or on-site)
Templates (links to material or pictures)
Relevant indicators (list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference)
Examples (external links) FOODITY PhotoVoice Workshops (citizen perspectives on food and data sovereignty, implemented in multiple countries): https://zenodo.org/records/15583853/files/Citizen%2520Empowerment%2520Handbook.pdf%3Fdownload%3D1

5.3.3 Household food waste “mini-audit”

Needs to be customized	Household food waste “mini-audit”	
Open source		
Digital or analogue: hybrid		
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualization, interaction setup) Measurement units, waste categories		
Target group (s): Citizen scientists / CSL participants		Data type collected
Time of use exploration, monitoring		Quantitative, such as weight, volume and qualitative composition based on reasoning and analysis
Timing (one-time data collection, before-after, continuous) Before-after, e.g. one week before and one week after an intervention – should be adapted to how BCIs are designed		Captures individual or household change
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions
/	/	
Effort (time, persons, material) Requires daily attention/routine during a limited period of time		
Detailed description Every day, participants record: 1. How much food was thrown away during the day. It is possible to do it throughout the day or recall main insights at the end of the day 2. Which categories of food were thrown away and why		What? A practical tracking exercise where participants record the types and amounts of food discarded in their households over a specific period (usually 7 days). Why? Provides data on the impact of behaviour change interventions (BCIs) and helps citizens understand their waste and recycling patterns.

3. Analyse the results at the end of the week.	How? Filling in a waste log and analysis of change over time
Templates (links to material or pictures) Simple grid template with date, food category, estimated amount, reason for disposal, and final destination	
Relevant indicators (list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference) Weight, volume and composition of food waste	
Examples (external links will be provide as this toolkit develops)	

5.3.4 Most Significant Change (MSC) stories

Ready-made /needs to be customized, specific domains must be defined per project	Most Significant Change (MSC) / Stories of Change		
License needed/open source (Public Domain - developed by Rick Davies and Jess Dart			
Digital/analogue: Hybrid			
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualization, interaction setup)			
Target group (s): Citizen scientists, stakeholder groups	Data type collected Qualitative Narratives: Structured stories including the context, the "Before," the "After," and the "Significance."		
Time of use can be used during or at the end of project usually covering prolonged periods of time	Documentary evidence of <i>why</i> specific stories were chosen, revealing the values and preferences of the project stakeholders. Visual/Multimedia: Photos or short video clips that illustrate the story		
Timing (can be one time or iterative to trace the change over time	Can capture both individual change and aggregated data		
Evaluation principle	Link to CSL interventions: Captures how systemic food interventions change individual lives		
acknowledging complexity	power sensitiveness	outcome- focused evaluation	
Effort (time, persons, material) Time: 1–2 months for a full cycle: domain definition, collection, selection, feedback; but could also be truncated into a workshop context in a mini-form Personnel: 1 Lead Facilitator; 1 Data Coordinator (to manage story storage); 3–5 Panel Members Material: audio recorders, story forms and common storage format			
Detailed description Participants are asked: "Looking back over the last 6 months, what do you think was the most significant change that occurred in your relationship with food?" Once stories are collected, a panel of stakeholders discusses them and chooses the stories that best represent the project's goals, documenting <i>why</i> that story was chosen.			What?
			Why?
			How?
Templates (links to material or pictures) https://www.betterevaluation.org/sites/default/files/EA_PM%2526E_toolkit_MSC_ma nual_for_publication.pdf			

A simple template can include a structured outline with three parts: 1. The situation before; 2. The change that happened, 3. Why is this change significant to the person?
Relevant indicators (to be added: list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference)
Examples (external links will be added as the toolkit develops)

5.4 TOOLS FOR CO-EVALUATION

5.4.1 Assessment rubrics

Ready-made (light customisation)	Assessment rubrics (example for FAIR “readiness” self-assessment)	
licence needed open source		
Digital (spreadsheet or web form); optional export to PDF for documentation		
Possible adaptation levels: Adapt to your data types (survey, photos, sensor, co-design outputs), required metadata fields, and local legal/ethical requirements. rubric criteria (e.g., FAIR dimensions), scoring scale (e.g., 0–2 / 1–5), weighting, and whether scoring is done per output or per WP deliverable.		
Target group (s): Project partners, CSL teams producing outputs and preparing datasets or materials.	Data type collected Structured checklist/rubric + score per dataset + links to evidence (metadata, licence, repository, documentation), + short justification text.	
Time of use: Before publishing/sharing data and at key reporting milestones (mid-term/final). Also useful right after data collection planning to identify gaps early.		
Timing: one-time data collection per data set; repeated as datasets evolve (versioning).	Aggregated data	
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions:
acknowledging complexity	/	outcome-focused evaluation
		Helps ensure re-use and interoperability across sites.
Effort: 15–30 min per dataset for first pass; 5–10 min for updates. More time if metadata/documentation needs to be created.		
Detailed description	What?	

<p>Use a simple traffic-light or 0–2 scoring per item. Agree on minimum thresholds (e.g., all “Reusable” items must be green before public release). Track improvements over time.</p> <p>In relation to FAIR readiness checks, assessment rubrics provide a short, standardised way to judge whether a dataset or output meets agreed quality criteria. Scores are submitted to AIT for aggregation and reporting; recurring gaps inform guidance and capacity building.</p>	<p>A scored checklist/rubric completed by the responsible partner with brief evidence notes.</p>
	<p>Why?</p> <p>To measure compliance indicators consistently (e.g., FAIR compliance), support continuous improvement of outputs, and reduce ambiguity in what “good quality” means across WPs.</p>
	<p>How?</p> <p>Define the rubric once. For each output, complete the rubric and attach evidence</p>
<p>Templates (links to material or picture</p>	
<p>Examples (external links</p>	

5.4.2 Stakeholder analysis

<p>Needs to be customized</p>	<p>Stakeholder Analysis</p>	
<p>open source</p>		
<p>Digital & analog</p>		
<p>Possible adaptation levels:</p>		
<p>Target group (s): Project partners, CSL teams.</p>	<p>Data type collected Stakeholder groups relevant for the project or workshop,</p>	
<p>Time of use: At the very beginning, before workshop or project starts</p>	<p>Captures individual change or aggregated data</p>	
<p>Timing: Before- the intervention/activity, regular updates advisable</p>		
<p>Evaluation principle It is crucial to ensure that the types of stakeholders participating in the co-creation workshops are as consistent as possible across the six CSLs, especially in phase 5 where stakeholders will assess the proposals developed by citizens and co-develop the foundation for the BCIs</p>	<p>Link to CSL interventions: to be added</p>	

acknowledging complexity	power sensitiveness	outcome-focused evaluation	
Effort (time, persons, material) Highly variable depending on the available resources.			
Detailed description Stakeholders are the people, groups, or organizations that are impacted by (or have an impact on) your project, organization, or work. Stakeholder mapping is the process of placing the attributes of the stakeholders onto a chart to visualize the data, compare the position of different stakeholders, and analyze stakeholders based on the attributes shown. Repetition of this exercise shows changes, which can be evaluated at the end of the project. Steps for stakeholder mapping 1) Brainstorming – Identify potential stakeholder categories and a wide range of potential stakeholders; your network is the best starting point. 2) Desk research: Map additional stakeholders from related domain. 3) Categorization & prioritization: categorize stakeholders according to various attributes as background, organization type, country, etc. and prioritize using a typology based on interest, influence, legitimacy, and urgency. 4) Updating –add, amend and update the stakeholder data regularly 5) Selection – select relevant stakeholders for the purpose of a co-creation		What?	
		Why?	
		How?	
Templates			
Examples (external links)			

5.4.3. Social network mapping

Needs to be customised	Social network mapping	
Licence needed/open source		
Digital and analogue		
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualisation, interaction setup) Customise: stakeholder categories, boundary (who is “in” the network), tie or connection types (collaboration/communication/resources/decision-making), direction (one-way/two-way), connection strength scale (e.g., 1–3), and whether mapping is done individually, in small groups, or as one shared map.		
Target group (s): Pilot coordinators and facilitators. CSL participants across stakeholder groups	Data type collected Semi-structured network data: visual map + structured tie list	

<p>Time of use (project phase – exploration, testing, implementation, monitoring, at the end of the activity)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploration: baseline ecosystem & existing relationships • Testing / early iterations: identify gaps and brokerage opportunities • Implementation monitoring: track changes across iterations/BCIs • End of iteration / before formative evaluation: consolidate “network change” evidence 	<p>(actor A–actor B–type–strength–direction) + short qualitative notes on changes (why ties formed/strengthened/weakened)→ can be digitalised</p>			
<p>Timing (one-time data collection, before-and-after, continuous) Before–after (baseline or early iteration workshop + post-iteration or post-BCI workshop).</p>	<p>Captures individual change or aggregated data</p>			
<p>Evaluation principle</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="151 891 922 972"> <tr> <td data-bbox="151 891 405 972">/</td> <td data-bbox="405 891 616 972">/</td> <td data-bbox="616 891 922 972">outcome-focused evaluation</td> </tr> </table>	/	/	outcome-focused evaluation	<p>Link to CSL interventions</p>
/	/	outcome-focused evaluation		
<p>Effort (time, persons, material) Time: 30–60 min per mapping session (incl. explanation + discussion); +15–30 min for documentation/digitising People: 1 facilitator; optional 1 note-taker; 1 person for synthesis (can be the same) Material: printed base sheet + stickers/markers OR digital board; optional “actor list” Data processing: light option (photos + transcription of ties) to medium (network metrics, comparison pre/post)</p>				
<p>Detailed description Social Network Mapping visualises relationships and collaborations between actors in a CSL ecosystem (citizens, research–policy, business, Civil Society Organizations). Done in early stages and repeated later, it helps to show whether the CSL has enabled new collaborations and improved two-way communication, and it highlights who is central, who is missing, and where</p>	<p>What? A participatory mapping exercise where participants place key actors on a map and draw connections between them (optionally coded by type, direction, and strength). Output is a network map plus a structured list of ties.</p> <p>Why? Makes “collaboration” and “communication” changes visible over time (pre/post).Helps identify inclusion gaps (missing groups, isolated actors) and potential gatekeeping/over-centralisation.</p> <p>How? actor types (citizens, researchers, policy, business, CSOs) and tie types (e.g., collaboration, information exchange, resources, decision-making). In a workshop, list actors and place them on a map (draw ties and label them (type, direction and strength).</p>			

power or access is uneven.	
Templates (links to material or pictures)	
Relevant indicators (list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference)	
Examples (external links) designpilot.info/techniken/tool-305-social-network-mapping/	

5.4.3 Outcome Harvesting (lightweight version)

Ready-made	Outcome harvesting	
Open source		
Digital/analogue		
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualisation, interaction setup)		
Target group (s): Pilot coordinators		Data type collected
Time of use: Formative and final evaluation		Qualitative outcome descriptions and contribution statements
Timing periodic, per evaluation round		Aggregated data
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions
acknowledging complexity	power sensitiveness	outcome-focused evaluation
Effort (time, persons, material) Dedicated workshop or section of a workshop		
Detailed description 1. Identify the change (The Outcome), e.g. "the local municipality decided to use SPOON's data for their new food strategy" 2. Identify the Contribution: "SPOON provided the data and invited the mayor to three workshops." 3. Verify: Check with the municipality that SPOON's data was indeed a key factor.		What? A method where evaluators and partners "harvest" observable changes in actors' behaviour and then work backwards to determine how SPOON contributed to those changes. Why? Identifies broader unintended or emergent outcomes How? Workshop setting
Templates (links to material or pictures) Outcome Statement table can include: What happened? Who did it? When? Where? How did SPOON help?		
Relevant indicators (list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference)		
Examples (external links)		

5.4.4 Ripple Effect Mapping

Needs to be customised		Ripple effect mapping	
Open source			
Both digital and analogue formats are possible.			
Possible adaptation levels (language, format, visualisation, interaction setup)			
Target group (s): CSL participants, evaluators		Data type collected Visual maps and qualitative linkages captures individual change or aggregated data	
Time of use: formative and final evaluation			
Timing one-time data collection			
Evaluation principle		Link to CSL interventions	
acknowledging complexity	power sensitiveness		
Effort (time, persons, material) Medium (2-hour group workshop), one facilitator with experience in applying the method, digital board or physical board with post-its of different colours			
Detailed description 1. Setup. Place the main project activity (like a CSL workshop or digital tool launch) in the centre of a large wall or digital board. This "core" anchors all the stories to come. 2. Pair and share. In pairs, participants spend 10 minutes interviewing each other about positive changes or experiences since the project began. Using Appreciative Inquiry, they focus on successes and specific moments of impact, not complaints. 3. Map the ripple effects, The group reconvenes and one by one, participants share stories as the facilitator draws outward "ripples" from the core: direct outputs (what happened), outcomes (personal changes), and wider impacts (who else benefited). Step 4: Connect the web. Spot intersections where one ripple touches another. Draw connecting lines to reveal the project's networked effects, social ties, and unexpected community value. Step 5: Reflect and close. Step back and discuss the insights and ways to sustain momentum post-project. You can use colours or colour lines to categorise impacts such as social, economic, environmental.		What? A participatory group mapping technique that starts with a core project activity and maps out the indirect effects that followed.	
		Why? Identify hidden and unobvious outcomes	
		How? A series of questions is followed by a individual collection of possible effects and their collaborative mapping and discussion	
Templates (links to material or pictures)			

Relevant indicators (list all relevant indicators for which this method is a primary reference)
Examples (external links) https://blueprintkentucky.mgcafe.uky.edu/community-arts/publications/ripple-effects-mapping https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12874-022-01570-4

6 CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

The SPOON Monitoring Toolkit translates one operational part of the SPOON Evaluation Framework into practice by providing a coherent set of “ready-to-use” monitoring tools, fiches and templates that help Citizen Science Labs and partners collect evidence in a consistent yet flexible way. It supports the evaluation logic by linking concrete data collection methods to the project’s pathways, questions and indicators, and by making it easier to document both *what was done* (process) and *what changed* (outcomes) across different local contexts.

Importantly, the Toolkit is designed as a **living document**. As SPOON activities evolve, it can be continuously refined based on implementation experience, feedback from citizen scientists and facilitators, and emerging learning needs. This includes adding new methods and tool descriptions, improving guidance on applicability and effort, and iterating templates to increase usability and comparability across sites. For the next iteration of the toolkit, additional sections in the method description form will be considered as follows:

- good practice examples and contact references to SPOON partners who have already applied the tool and/or have experience with the more complex tools (to act as support or for tailored peer-learning)
- indications on group size and settings where the tools work best
- differentiation of direct and indirect monitoring methods.

In this way, the Toolkit not only supports robust monitoring during the project, but also strengthens long-term learning, replication and scaling by providing a shared, adaptable “evaluation infrastructure” for food systems transformation initiatives.

Building on the rollout of this Toolkit, upcoming steps will focus on training and capacity building for pilot coordinators to ensure monitoring tools are applied consistently across all CSLs. The next phase begins in Q1 2026 (M16) with the Baseline Evaluation, which assesses the starting conditions across the CSLs and their pilot regions while providing coordinators with initial implementation and evaluation guidance. This phase is supported by planned CSL interviews and a training session as part of formative evaluation to align data collection at each CSL. Following this, the monitoring process follows a phased approach: Formative Evaluation is applied as a participatory, reflexive exercise conducted annually beginning in 2026 to track progress and refine impact potential. These formative evaluations act as a learning process between evaluators and CSLs, utilizing co-created KPIs and feedback loops after each CSL iteration to ensure alignment with project objectives. Each cycle continues with targeted data collection in line with the iteration topics and knowledge transfer throughout 2027, culminating in the post-intervention (BCI-POST) and final evaluation workshops in 2028.

The publishing of this toolkit will be followed with setting the necessary data infrastructure in collaboration with WP2 and capacity building for work package leads and pilot coordinators.

5 ANNEXES

6.1 INDICATOR CATEGORIES

These categories help organise data collection and disaggregation from the inside of the database. They are provided for general orientation by project partners. This does not include partner-facing categories outlined earlier.

Category	What does this mean?
EQ	Each evaluation has one or several indicators.
Code	Every indicator has a code that serves as a unique identifier and also allows for easy tracing.
Class	Indicator class output, outcomes or process-based.
Data flow	One of the three data flows is selected.
Linked results	Every indicator is tagged for relevant project results that it helps to trace, if applicable. This also helps with identifying partners responsible for collecting and reporting data on a specific indicator.
Rounds	Data collection rounds
CSL tags	Allow to mark indicators applicable to specific labs only
Type	Top-down (project-driven), bottom-up (CSL-driven) or exploratory (open-ended and subject to emerging evidence).
SDG tags	Applied to specific indicators if relevant
Tags	Other tags can be introduced by AIT or other project partners when relevant.
Data	Qualitative or quantitative.
Status	Open/closed for data collection

6.2 BASELINE EVALUATION TEMPLATE

The template provides an outlook on how the evaluation team analyses the underlying baseline conditions in each pilot region and lab before the project start. Since no established monitoring arrangements are expected to exist at the project start, the baseline evaluation aims to provide a sufficiently comprehensive outlook on the context that serves as the reference for further contextualising interim and final project outcomes with regard to each pilot region. The baseline evaluation covers the period before the project start and may only leverage select information obtained after the project start, if it applies to that period.

Any activities following the start of the project will thus already be part of the first formative evaluation. The baseline evaluation will account for possible changes in team composition within the lab. While the baseline ideas about what SPOON is about and how it is contextualised locally may significantly differ from the understanding of the project at a given point, it is important to account for those differences as part of the evaluation process.

The questions outlined below will form the basis of engaging pilot coordinators of specific CSLs. These questions can be further adjusted if certain data is already available or if there are specific local conditions that need to be better understood or elaborated. Baseline evaluation is expected to support preparation for the CLS iterations and the first formative evaluation.

Guiding question	How to respond
What are the most important facts about your lab that define how it is set up and functions?	Provide a short narrative description of how the lab is set up and how it functions. Use available evidence and reference any existing lab documentation. Where relevant, explain how the lab worked before SPOON and what SPOON adds.
How many people form the core team of the lab at project start?	Report on the number of people in the CSL core delivery team at project start. Count only those with ongoing responsibilities. State the counting rules you used.
In which year was the lab founded?	Provide the year the lab or its host initiative was established. If the CSL builds on an earlier lab, report both years and clarify which one you use as a baseline.
How many organisations are formally involved in operating the lab at project start?	List the organisations that formally operate or co-host the CSL at baseline and report the count. Include key delivery partners if they have defined responsibilities.

<p>Which baseline conditions have an impact on how your lab is positioned to deliver impact from the perspective of the SPOON project?</p>	<p>Describe the lab's background prior to SPOON. Provide a concise overview of the key contextual conditions you expect to shape participation, behaviour change, and data sharing in your CSL. Focus on what is distinctive about your location and what this implies for CSL design and for interpreting results.</p>
<p>What elements of local food culture and broader social norms around food may influence your CSL activities within SPOON?</p>	<p>Reflect on locally salient food traditions and norms that may enable or constrain healthy and sustainable choices. Consider, for example, strong culinary traditions and communal eating practices, preferences or stigma around specific foods, everyday routines around buying, cooking, and eating, and how healthy and sustainable food is perceived locally. Provide illustrative examples from your context.</p>
<p>Which national, regional, or municipal food policies and strategies are most relevant to your CSL focus, and how might they influence your activities?</p>	<p>Summarise the most relevant policy priorities and any active strategies, councils, or programmes the CSL can connect to. Note whether the CSL is embedded in municipal strategies or relies more on civic initiatives. Where possible, name the specific policy documents you draw on.</p>
<p>Which policy strategies or programmes were identified as baseline context for your CSL?</p>	<p>List policy strategies, programmes, or formal plans that are directly relevant to your CSL focus at the project start. Count each document or programme once and list its level, for example, national, regional, or municipal.</p>
<p>What is your experience within the lab with engaging stakeholders into your activities locally?</p>	<p>Describe how people typically engage in community initiatives locally and what tends to enable or hinder participation based on your experience prior to SPOON. Consider trust, time availability, prior experience with citizen science or living labs, and any groups that are harder to reach.</p>
<p>What are the CSL's initial focus areas and priority challenges, and how do they relate to the SPOON pathways and iteration?</p>	<p>Describe the significance of SPOON to your overall lab activities. Explain which pathways and expected project results seem most and least significant for your context and why. Indicate what you consider achievable within the first iteration.</p>
<p>What information on data sharing culture and practices did you have before the project started?</p>	<p>Summarise existing knowledge and prior experiences relevant to data sharing, including local concerns about surveillance, misuse, or commercial capture. Note any widely known data incidents that shape expectations and any previous trust-building efforts.</p>

<p>How do cost and affordability conditions shape access to healthy and sustainable food in your context?</p>	<p>Describe the relative affordability of healthier and more sustainable options compared with cheaper alternatives. Note which groups are most affected and how this is connected to food insecurity or dietary constraints. Describe this based on available knowledge before the project starts.</p>
<p>What socio-economic inequalities and vulnerabilities are most relevant for your region?</p>	<p>Describe key vulnerabilities, for example income constraints, unemployment, rural and urban divides, migrant status, or stigma, and how these affect food access, participation capacity, and digital engagement.</p>
<p>Which structural factors in the local food environment are most likely to enable or constrain change based on available knowledge at the start of the project?</p>	<p>Describe structural features such as supermarket dominance versus alternative outlets, transport and mobility constraints, spatial distribution of outlets, and the presence of food deserts or food swamps. Explain how these conditions shape feasible interventions and data collection.</p>
<p>What is the baseline level of trust in institutions and governance relevant to SPOON, and how might this affect participation and data sharing?</p>	<p>Summarise who is trusted and why, and where scepticism is expected, for example, towards sustainability claims, municipal programmes, or platforms. Indicate implications for recruitment, consent, retention, and collaboration with food actors and public authorities.</p>
<p>What does your stakeholder mapping show about key stakeholder groups, motivations, needs, and barriers, and what opportunities and risks does it entail?</p>	<p>Summarise the main stakeholder groups, their motivations and barriers, and the priorities that matter most for engagement. Where possible, draw on existing stakeholder mapping outputs, including any cross-CSL stakeholder mapping, to avoid duplicate reporting. Note implications for collaboration and synergy work.</p>
<p>How many stakeholder groups and organisations are prioritised for engagement at baseline?</p>	<p>Report on the number of stakeholder groups and the number of prioritised organisations identified at baseline. Count each group and each organisation once. Where possible, classify organisations by type, for example, municipality, NGO, business, or research.</p>
<p>Which other baseline evidence is available that would be relevant to better understand the local context?</p>	<p>List the main internal sources you will draw on, for example, CSL protocol notes, workshop reports, socio-demographic templates, and reporting templates. Indicate what will be extracted and what still needs primary data collection. Note any additional priorities, needs, or goals relevant to the state of the lab and the pilot region at the project start.</p>
<p>What are the key knowledge, capacity, or other gaps that you expect the project to address?</p>	<p>Describe key expectations and aspirations regarding SPOON from the perspective of your lab and region. Indicate which gaps are most urgent for your context and which can be addressed later in the project.</p>

CONSORTIUM

SPOON

KEEP IN TOUCH:

[@SPOON-PROJECT](#)

INFO@SPOONPROJECT.EU

[@SPOON_EU](#)